

Track Recommendations Moderate Socioeconomic Differences during the Transition from Primary to Secondary Education

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Data availability

Data will be publicly available on the study’s project page at the Open Science Framework (OSF)

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Abstract

This study investigates how track recommendations moderate socioeconomic status (SES) differences during the transition from primary to secondary education in Hungary. Using survey data on teachers' track recommendations and students' application intentions, combined with administrative data on application behaviour and actual admissions, the study finds that SES disparities are concentrated among students recommended for an academic track. Within this group, the average probabilities of intending to apply, applying, and being admitted are higher for high-SES students than for their low-SES peers. In contrast, among students who are not recommended the academic track, SES differences are substantively smaller and statistically not significant. The contrasting SES gaps between students recommended/not recommended for the academic track result in a positive interaction effect on admission to academic-track secondary schools. Taken together, the findings suggest that teacher agency in shaping SES disparities in academic track enrolment may be more limited than previously assumed, as even when students are recommended for the academic track, cultural and institutional factors may still hinder their intention to apply, their actual application, and eventual admission to academic-track secondary schools.

Keywords

Track recommendations, Transition from primary to secondary education, Socioeconomic status (SES) differences, Application intentions, Applications to the academic track, Admission to the academic track, Moderation, Hungary

Introduction

The socioeconomic status (SES)-related differences in teachers' track recommendations are a key driver of students' unequal allocation between different secondary tracks (Batruch et al. 2023). Teachers often recommend the vocational secondary track to high-performing low-SES students, whereas their high-SES peers with similar performance are more frequently encouraged to pursue the academic secondary track (Timmermans et al. 2015). Teachers' biased track recommendations have been documented in observational studies from France (Barg 2013) and Flanders (Boone and Van Houtte 2013), as well as in experimental research in Germany (Sprietsma 2013; Wenz and Hoening 2020), the Netherlands (Van Ewijk 2011), and Hungary (Kisfalusi et al. 2024). Particularly, the SES differences in track recommendations have been interpreted as the *tertiary effect* of social origin (Esser 2016; Helbig and Morar 2018), extending Boudon's seminal distinction between social origin's primary and secondary effects (Boudon 1974).

Whether binding or non-binding, track recommendations shape SES differences in the transition to the academic secondary track in the context of most European countries. Through the provision of formal and binding track recommendations—as observed in German federal states including Bavaria, Thuringia, and Saxony (Grewenig 2022), in the Netherlands (Driessen et al. 2008; Geven et al. 2021), and Luxembourg (Glock et al. 2012)—teachers directly shape students' application intentions, application behaviour and ultimate admission to the academic secondary track. However, teachers also indirectly shape these outcomes, whether in the form of formal and non-binding recommendations, as seen in Italy (Bonizzoni et al. 2016), or informal and non-binding recommendations, as observed in Flanders (Boone and Van Houtte

2013; Boone et al. 2018) and in Hungary (Horn et al. 2016; Keller 2023), since track recommendation can raise self-confidence (Tolsma et al. 2010), provide access to information (Barone et al. 2018) and empower students to pursue a given secondary track (Keller et al. 2022).

In both binding and non-binding regimes, being recommended for the academic track provides access to advantageous resources that can lead to the accumulation of further advantages. Conversely, not being recommended for the academic track represents a missed opportunity and a detachment from potential resources, which can lead to the accumulation of further disadvantages.

Much prior scholarship implicitly assumes that SES differences in academic track enrolment would be reduced in the absence of teachers' socioeconomically biased track recommendations (Esser 2016; Helbig and Morar 2018; Batruch et al. 2023). However, this assumption remains largely untested because the majority of research has focused narrowly on teachers' track recommendations rather than broadly on the entire transition process. This narrow perspective fails to account for potential SES-related differences in subsequent outcomes during the transition process—such as application intentions, application behaviour, and eventual admission to the academic secondary track—between students with and without an academic track recommendation.

This study challenges the implicit assumptions of earlier research and also broadens the scope to examine the entire transition process. It examines how track recommendations moderate SES differences—measured by mother's education (Erola et al. 2016)—during the transition from primary to secondary education in Hungary, where recommendations are non-binding and informal, yet teachers frequently express their opinions on students' track placement.

The study draws on a unique dataset comprising 39 homeroom teachers and 552 eighth-grade students—those in their final year of primary school. Teachers were asked to recommend a secondary track to each student three months before the official application deadline for secondary education. Subsequently, a student survey captured students' application intentions. These data were then merged with administrative records on students' actual application behaviour and admission outcomes.

The findings corroborate previous research by showing that, within the same classroom and after controlling for students' grade point averages (GPAs), teachers are more likely to recommend the academic track to high-SES students than to low-SES students. However, the benefits of being recommended for an academic track are not equally distributed: low-SES students derive less advantage from such recommendations than their high-SES peers. Specifically, the gap in application intentions, application behaviour, and eventual admission between low- and high-SES students is small and statistically insignificant when neither group is recommended for the academic track. In contrast, when both groups are recommended for the academic track, the SES gaps in these outcomes are large and statistically significant. Notably, the difference in SES gaps between students with and without academic track recommendations is positive and statistically significant regarding actual admission to the academic track, and it is positive but statistically insignificant for application intentions and behaviour.

The positive interaction suggests that teachers' track recommendations moderate the relationship between students' SES and their admission to the academic track. Particularly since the SES gap is large among students who are recommended for the academic track, the role of teacher agency in generating SES differences—either by withholding such recommendations or embedding them with bias—appears less significant than previously assumed. The

statistically significant positive interaction between track recommendation and SES concerning admission is particularly noteworthy, as admission ultimately shapes students' future educational trajectories. Consequently, in the context of admission, academic track recommendations appear to exacerbate, rather than mitigate, pre-existing SES differences.

The generalisability of the findings may be limited. The results presented in this study are observational rather than causal. Therefore, these findings should be regarded as a tentative contribution until more robust evidence emerges to address the gap in the literature on how teachers' track recommendations moderate SES differences during the transition from primary to secondary education.

Literature review

Mechanisms behind the evolution of SES differences during the transition from primary to secondary education

During the transition from primary to secondary education, track recommendations may act as a moderator if students' SES and teachers' recommendations interact to influence outcomes such as application intentions, application behaviour, and actual admission. Notably, being recommended for an academic track can both mitigate and exacerbate SES differences, leading to a negative or positive interaction between teachers' track recommendations and students' SES.

Interaction effects—whether positive or negative—can mask the underlying dynamics of SES differences between students who are recommended/not recommended for the academic track. Intuitively, four logical scenarios can be deduced, since both receiving and not receiving a recommendation may be associated with either widening or narrowing SES differences, as outlined in Table 1.

	Not receiving an academic track recommendation	Receiving an academic track recommendation
Positive Interaction: Track Recommendation \times SES (<i>widening SES differences</i>)	compensatory advantage mechanism	cumulative (dis)advantage mechanism
Negative Interaction: Track Recommendation \times SES (<i>narrowing SES differences</i>)	disadvantage saturation mechanism advantage-leveraging mechanism	great equaliser mechanism

Table 1: Logically deduced mechanisms influencing SES differences during the transition to secondary school

Differences between high- and low-SES students may widen when students are not recommended for the academic track. According to the *compensatory advantage mechanism*, students from high-SES backgrounds are better protected against the negative consequences of such adverse outcomes (Bernardi 2014). This is because high-SES families actively mobilise their resources to maintain and reinforce their children's educational advantages (Lucas 2001). When high-SES students encounter a setback that could jeopardise their academic trajectory, their families often respond by combining academic support with broader social and cultural

resources to help them recover and stay on track. In contrast, low-SES families typically lack access to such resources, as these families are less able to provide academic assistance and can mobilise their limited social and cultural capital less effectively to mitigate the effects of failure. As a result, not receiving a recommendation for the academic track tends to have less severe consequences for high-SES students but more detrimental effects for those from low-SES backgrounds. This dynamic contributes to a sizable SES gap that increasingly favours high-SES students over time.

However, not being recommended for the academic track could also lead to narrowing SES differences. According to the *disadvantage saturation mechanism*, individuals already experiencing substantial disadvantage may be less affected by additional setbacks, as their circumstances are already severely constrained (Hannon 2003; Pinchak and Swisher 2022). A related idea, known as the *advantage-leveraging mechanism*, frames this from the perspective of high-SES students, suggesting that they may have more to lose when exposed to disadvantage (Levy et al. 2019). Because high-SES students are not challenged by multiple threats, a single emerging setback may cause a relatively larger decline. Importantly, both mechanisms imply that although low-SES students continue to fall behind, they may be relatively less harmed by a failure than their high-SES peers, potentially leading to a small SES gap (Pinchak and Swisher 2022). Applying these ideas to the case of not being recommended for the academic track—a potential setback that students experience—suggests that, although high-SES students still outperform their low-SES peers in later educational outcomes, their advantage may be relatively small.

Turning to the situation when students are recommended for the academic track, this may initially widen the existing SES gap. The mechanism of *cumulative advantage* suggests that high-SES students are more likely to experience growing benefits over time, as their initial advantages grant them access to resources that further reinforce their favourable position (DiPrete and Eirich 2006). The parallel *cumulative disadvantage mechanism* highlights the persistence of early setbacks since they induce a downward spiral, harming low-SES individuals even when they are comparable to high-SES peers in terms of observable characteristics (Pais 2014; Kallio et al. 2016). Thus, the cumulative disadvantage mechanism not only implies the widening of initial disadvantages but also suggests that this disproportionately harms those already in less favourable positions (Layte and Whelan 2002; Hannon 2003; DiPrete and Eirich 2006).

The concept of disproportionality can be traced back to Blau and Duncan's idea of cumulative disadvantage, which was explored through their comparison of occupational attainment and social mobility between disadvantaged and non-disadvantaged social groups in American society, such as Blacks and Whites. They observed that, even after accounting for educational disadvantages and low social origins, Black individuals still began their careers in lower-status positions more frequently than their white counterparts (Blau and Duncan 1967, p. 204). Accordingly, Blau and Duncan argued that educational advancement yielded fewer returns for Black individuals, both in terms of occupational attainment and social mobility (Blau and Duncan 1967, p. 210). In other words, the disadvantaged group derived fewer benefits from education, while the same level of advancement moved the careers of members of the advantaged group forward to a greater extent. This interpretation of cumulative disadvantage has since been proposed as a framework that may be generalised and extended to educational inequality, particularly in analyses of how tracking and track placement decisions reproduce social disparities (DiPrete and Eirich 2006, p. 273).

Intuitively, being recommended the academic track may also narrow SES differences—a notion known as the “great equaliser”—though this mechanism is often criticised theoretically (Bernardi and Ballarino 2016). Nevertheless, the idea that track recommendation acts as a social

equaliser suggests that if two students are recommended for the academic track, they will have equal educational prospects, regardless of differences such as social background. From this perspective, the recommendation of the academic track levels the playing field by aligning the life chances of unequally positioned individuals.

The coexistence of several mechanisms highlights the need to explore whether the observed patterns in SES differences—based on academic track recommendation—align with specific theoretical mechanisms.

Teachers' biased track recommendations

Prior research has explored various explanations for the SES differences in teachers' track recommendations, considering factors such as students' ability and school performance (Boone and Van Houtte 2013; Timmermans et al. 2016; Barg 2013), work behaviour (Krolak-Schwerdt et al. 2018), reliability and accuracy (Klapproth et al. 2012), self-confidence and effort (Driessen et al. 2008), the ability to work independently (Boone and Van Houtte 2013), parental support (Krolak-Schwerdt et al. 2018), parental involvement (Barg 2013) and home environment (Driessen et al. 2008). Besides these student characteristics, teachers' prejudices (Glock, 2015) and the classroom context (Caro et al. 2009; Boone et al. 2018) also influence track recommendations. Taken together, although these factors influence track recommendations, they do not appear to account for biases in teachers' track recommendations. This suggests that their role in mediating the relationship between SES and track recommendations is rather limited (Batruch et al. 2023).

Experiments suggest that situational factors affect teachers' track recommendations. Glock et al. (2012) manipulated teachers' accountability in Luxembourg by assigning them to one of three experimental conditions. In the low accountability condition, teachers gave their track recommendations to one of their colleagues to pass on to students. In the high-accountability condition, teachers imagined being solely accountable for making track-related decisions. In the medium accountability condition, teachers advised a teacher council on their track recommendations. The authors found that teachers' track recommendations were biased only in the low accountability condition. The results of Glock et al. (2012) suggest that teachers' track recommendations may be more biased when teachers are relieved of the responsibility for their decisions and, therefore, their recommendations have a low stake.

In low-stakes experimental scenarios, various experimental studies have detected ethnic discrimination in track recommendations. These experiments randomly assign minority and majority names to student test assignments, which teachers then evaluate. For instance, Sprietsma (2013) found that students with Turkish names were less likely to be recommended for the academic secondary track than German students, even when their performance was identical. Similarly, Wenz and Hoenig (2020) revealed that Turkish students were perceived as less likely to succeed in the academic secondary track than students from the German upper-middle class. Comparable findings are also available for Hungary, where experimental evidence showed that Hungarian Roma students were more likely to be recommended the less prestigious vocational track than their equally performing non-Roma Hungarian counterparts (Kisfalusi et al. 2024).

In sum, however, the effect of migration or ethnic background on receiving an academic track recommendation has been found to be modest in prior literature, with raw differences of 5 percentage points between German and Turkish names (Sprietsma 2013) and 4 points between non-Roma and Roma names in Hungary (Kisfalusi et al. 2024). Thus, the relatively modest

findings of prior studies highlight the need for new directions in future research (Batruch et al. 2023). Besides focusing on why SES differences exist in track recommendations, research should also explore how track recommendations moderate SES differences during this critical transition—an area that has received comparatively little attention in previous studies.

Track recommendations in Hungary

Two experimental studies have examined teachers' track recommendations in Hungary, focusing specifically on ethnic minority differences. Both studies employed fictitious tests with randomly assigned names to explore the causal impact of discrimination on track recommendations.

Bruneau et al. (2020) conducted vignette experiments involving pre-service teachers—that is, university students training to become teachers. Participants evaluated 22 student profiles on a scale from 0 to 100, assessing the appropriateness of three different educational tracks for the fictitious students. The findings revealed discrimination against Roma students. For instance, in Study 1b (N of teachers = 161), Roma students were rated as significantly more suited for the lower-level track (mean for Roma = 47; mean for non-Roma = 44) but significantly less suited for the higher-level track (mean for Roma = 28; mean for non-Roma = 31).

Kisfalusi et al. (2024) analysed a larger sample of 413 primary school teachers who evaluated six mathematics, literacy, and grammar tests associated with fictitious, randomised student names and then recommended them high school tracks. Their results showed that 70% of non-Roma students were recommended for the non-academic track, compared with 66% of Roma students.

Together, studies that have employed causal estimation strategies have documented the presence of ethnic discrimination in track recommendations in Hungary, although the substantive effect size is relatively small. However, no comparable experimental study has examined social SES differences in track recommendations within the Hungarian context.

Institutional context

Tracked secondary education in Hungary

In Hungary, students transition from primary to secondary education at the age of 14 after eight years of undivided primary education. Students can choose between three different tracks.

The most knowledge-intensive and selective academic track (*gimnázium*) provides a four-year education that ends with the high-school final examination (*érettségi*), a prerequisite for subsequent enrolment in tertiary education. The academic track gives students the highest chance of entering tertiary education.

In contrast, the vocational track (*szakképző iskola*) provides a three-year education that does not end with a high-school final examination, so students who graduate from this track cannot enter tertiary education directly. Vocational schools train blue-collar workers who often perform manual labour.

The third track at the secondary level is called *technikum*, which mixes the features of the academic and vocational tracks. This track lasts five years. However, in contrast to the academic track, students who graduate from the technikum track usually have a lower chance of later admission to university because curricula here place greater emphasis on vocational subjects, leading students to study general subjects with less intensity. There are also differences between the technikum and vocational tracks. Students on the technikum track receive a vocational diploma in the fifth year, which qualifies them as skilled in occupations that are primarily related to administrative, managerial, and controlling tasks, as opposed to the occupations accessible through the vocational track.

The vocational education offered in the vocational track and in the technikum is taught within a dual education system. Apprenticeships, which are part of the training, are often organised by firms where students can acquire and practice the practical skills required in the profession. During the apprenticeship period, students can receive a considerable stipend and even a salary later on, which is a clear financial incentive for many students and deters them from choosing the more theoretical and learning-oriented academic track that does not offer financial compensation during the years of education. As a result, many low-SES students opt for the vocational track, which offers almost immediate earning potential.

The application process

Students apply for secondary education by creating a preference list of schools they would like to attend. They can freely list any number of secondary schools. Students submit their preference list to a clearing house and also apply individually to each school on their list. As a result, the secondary school is aware of the pool of applicants but not of the students' order of preference; i.e., schools do not know where students have ranked them.

Students are admitted to secondary schools based on three criteria—grades, admission test scores, and oral interviews—which are applied in three different combinations. All schools take into account students' grades in core subjects. According to the first admission approach, admission is based solely on these grades. The second admission approach combines grades with scores from a nationally coordinated written test in mathematics and Hungarian. A small number of schools are permitted to conduct local oral interviews and include the results alongside grades and written test scores. Thus, the third admission approach uses all three criteria—grades, test scores, and interview performance—in admission decisions.

The construction of the preference list is important. Students are admitted to the highest-ranked school on their preference list for which they meet the admission requirements, even if the lower-ranked schools would also accept them following a Gale–Shapley matching mechanism (Gale and Shapley 1962). For example, if the highest-ranked school to which a student qualifies is their second choice on the preference list, they are admitted there, even though they also meet the admission requirements for their third choice, because the nationally coordinated matching algorithm ultimately matches students to only one school. Administrative data show that approximately 70% of students are admitted to their first-choice school.

The role of teachers in the application process

The homeroom teacher's role in the application process is crucial for several reasons. First, it is the homeroom teachers' duty to officially send all of their students' applications to the schools to which they have applied and to submit the students' ranked preference lists to the clearing house. Therefore, homeroom teachers are fully aware of the students' application intentions. Self-reported responses from a nationally representative teacher survey carried out among 413 Hungarian homeroom teachers in 2021 indicate that 93% of teachers had been asked by their students for advice during the application process, and 78% of all teachers have at least once recommended applying to a school other than the one to which the student originally intended to.

Second, although teachers do not formulate binding track recommendations for students, the same teacher survey revealed that 20% of teachers usually encourage students to choose a stronger school than the one they had originally planned to apply to. At the same time, 7% of teachers usually discourage students from choosing a stronger school and encourage them to choose a weaker one. The remaining 73% of teachers discourage and encourage students with equal probability, without resorting to any primary strategy. These figures underscore that teachers frequently communicate their track recommendations to students.

Third, homeroom teachers of eighth-grade students organise orientation days for their students in their local primary school. In addition to this, homeroom teachers also advertise to their students the open days organised by secondary schools. Both occasions provide interested students with deeper insight and a more qualitative impression of secondary schools. These occasions are further opportunities for teachers to express their expectations to students and encourage or discourage them.

In sum, although track recommendations are non-binding and informal in the Hungarian context, teachers are typically aware of their students' application plans, offer guidance, and either encourage or discourage these plans. Through this involvement, the structure of the application process provides teachers with multiple opportunities to voice their opinions on students' track choices—beyond the more informal moments when teachers may express their recommendations in less direct ways.

Data, measurement, and empirical analysis

All supplementary materials, datasets, and analytical scripts are openly accessible on the project's page hosted by the Open Science Framework (OSF): <https://osf.io/8msbr/>. Ethical approval for this research was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the ELTE Centre for Social Sciences, Budapest.

For the purpose of implementing a pre-registered field experiment on track choice in the fall of 2021 (Keller 2025), invitation letters were sent to all Hungarian primary schools, and eighth-grade homeroom teachers were asked to participate. Teachers indicated their willingness to participate in the project by completing three tasks. First, they completed an online background questionnaire in which they indicated the secondary track they had recommended to each of their students. Second, teachers provided the grades that each student had earned at the end of the previous academic year in the seventh grade. Third, teachers were also asked to coordinate the completion of an approximately 45-minute-long online student questionnaire on educational plans and school choice. To compensate teachers for their efforts, they could participate in a lottery in which three teachers were randomly selected to win a tablet worth 200 EUR in local currency.

Both teachers and students completed the questionnaires between November 18 and December 22, 2021, approximately two to three months before the official application deadline in February 2022. A total of 39 teachers from 38 schools participated in the survey, completing the teacher questionnaire and facilitating student participation. Together, they provided data on 592 students. Teacher-reported information and students' self-reported data were merged with administrative records on application behaviour and actual secondary school enrolment. This study analyses data from students whose application and admission records were available in the administrative dataset and who had non-missing track recommendations (N = 552).

As a school-level comparison in Table A1 in the Appendix shows, the schools participating in the survey are not nationally representative; they are more likely to be small village schools. Students in the sample also have significantly lower average mathematics and reading comprehension performance, and their SES index is significantly lower than that of students in non-sample schools.

As a student-level comparison in Table A2 of the Appendix shows, students participating in the survey are not significantly different from all eighth-grade Hungarian primary school students in terms of their school grades (GPA) and application/admission to academic track secondary schools. However, it should be noted that participating students were seven percentage points less likely to apply to academic track secondary schools and seven percentage points less likely to be admitted to one than non-participating students, which is a substantial difference, albeit lacking statistical significance.

Outcome variables

This study utilises outcome variables measured at different stages of the transition process. Specifically, it examines three key outcomes: (1) the intention to apply, (2) actual applications, and (3) admission to academic-track secondary schools. All outcome variables are binary.

Students' application intentions were measured in the student questionnaire with the question: "During the secondary school application process this year, which school track would you most like to apply to?" Students could choose from three available tracks. The academic track was coded '1', while the other two tracks—including the response "I don't know"—were coded '0'.

Survey data were combined with administrative register data on students' application behaviour. The variable *applied to schools on the academic track* was coded '1' if a student listed an academic track secondary school as their first choice, and '0' if their first choice was a vocational or mixed-track secondary school.

The outcome of the admission process, indicating the school to which students were admitted, also comes from registry data. The variable *admitted to a school on the academic track* was coded '1' if a student was admitted to an academic track secondary school, and '0' otherwise.

Missing values in the outcome variables were not replaced.

Variables of interest

Teacher-given track recommendation and students’ socioeconomic status (SES) are the two variables of interest. The source of these variables varies. Track recommendations are reported in the teacher questionnaire, while students reported their SES.

Teachers’ non-binding and informal track recommendations were provided in response to the following question in the teacher questionnaire: “Please indicate in the table below, for each of your students in your classroom, the particular secondary track that you would recommend to them upon completion of primary education in grade 8.” Teachers could recommend any of the three available tracks for each student. The academic track was assigned a value of ‘1’, and the remaining two tracks were coded ‘0’.

Students’ SES was measured by the mother’s highest level of education—a commonly used indicator in the literature, as parental education strongly predicts children’s outcomes, with maternal education being particularly influential in early childhood (Erola et al. 2016). Students whose mothers had completed tertiary education were classified as ‘high-SES’, while those with a lower level of education (uncompleted/completed primary or secondary education) were classified as ‘middle/low-SES’. For simplicity, this latter group will be referred to as ‘low-SES students’ throughout the study. Missing SES values were replaced with zero, with dummy variables controlling for missingness to retain all observations.

Control variables

Control variables included students’ grade point average (GPA), gender, age, behaviour, and diligence grades. These variables were held constant during estimations. All of these variables are teacher-reported.

Students’ seventh-grade GPA was reported by their teachers, who used grades from students’ end-of-term report cards. This is the average of five grades—mathematics, Hungarian grammar (writing), Hungarian literature (reading), history, and a foreign language—received in the report cards for that year. The grades for each subject range from 1 (the lowest grade) to 5 (the highest grade). Thus, a higher GPA represents better academic performance.

The variable ‘female’ was coded ‘1’ if the student was female and ‘0’ if the student was male. Age is the difference between the official secondary school application deadline and the student’s birthday, divided by 365.

Students’ teacher-reported grades for school behaviour and diligence also served as control variables. Behaviour and diligence grades were integers, ranging from 2 to 5.

Missing values in all control variables were replaced with zero, and separate dummy variables controlled for missing status in the models. This method was preferred to avoid losing observations.

The descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study are presented in Table 2. Figure A1 in the Appendix shows the raw means of the dependent variable according to SES and track recommendation.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the variables analysed in this study

	Mean	SD	% of missing
Teacher-reported variables			

<i>Academic track recommendation</i>	0.28	0.45	0.0%
<i>GPA, grade 7</i>	3.52	0.96	0.0%
<i>Diligence grade, grade 7</i>	3.83	0.95	0.7%
<i>Behaviour grade, grade 7</i>	4.19	0.87	0.7%
<i>Female</i>	0.48	0.50	0.0%
<i>Age at application deadline</i>	14.06	2.72	0.0%
Student-reported variables			
<i>Intends to apply to an academic track secondary school (OUTCOME)</i>	0.29	0.45	0.0%
<i>Students' SES: Tertiary-educated mother</i>	0.21	0.41	10.5%
Registry data			
<i>Applied to schools on the academic track (OUTCOME)</i>	0.26	0.44	0.0%
<i>Admitted to a school on the academic track (OUTCOME)</i>	0.24	0.43	0.0%

N = 552 students

Descriptive evidence

Students recommended for an academic track had a GPA that was 1.4 units higher on average ($p < 0.01$) than those who were not recommended. However, within both groups, the GPA difference between low- and high-SES students did not vary, suggesting that recommendations were given at similar GPA levels regardless of SES. This implies that low-SES students were not required to outperform their high-SES peers to be considered for the academic track, nor did teachers recommend the academic track to low-SES students with lower GPAs.

Figure 1 shows the share of students recommended, intending to apply, applying, and admitted to the academic track. These shares are similar in magnitude, differing by no more than 5 percentage points. This suggests that primary school teachers (through track recommendations), students (via application intentions and behaviours), and secondary school teachers (through admissions) all assess a similar proportion of students as eligible for the academic track.

Figure 1. Share of students (with 95% CIs) recommended, intending to apply, applying, and admitted to the academic track

Figure 2 shows the SES gaps, calculated as the within-classroom marginal mean differences between low- and high-SES students, adjusted for students’ GPAs and estimated using classroom-fixed effects. Statistically significant SES differences range from 13 percentage points (for application intention and admission to academic-track secondary schools) to 17 percentage points (for actual application). The SES gap in teachers’ academic-track recommendations is 14 percentage points. This figure supports previous research, showing that teachers are more likely to recommend the academic track to high-SES students than to their low-SES peers (Batruch et al. 2023).

However, although the SES gap appears similar in magnitude across the four measures, the average marginal differences may conceal important variations, which are further examined in the empirical analysis.

Note: This figure shows the SES gap, net of students' GPAs expressed in percentage points. The SES differences are estimated with classroom-fixed effects OLS regressions, with standard errors clustered at the school level. The SES differences presented here are statistically significant at the 5% significance level, as the 95% confidence interval around the point estimate does not cross the vertical line marked at 0 on the y-axis.

Figure 2. SES gaps (in percentage points, with 95% CIs) in track recommendation, application intention, application behaviour, and admission to academic-track secondary schools

Identification of moderation

A moderator affects the relationship between two variables, resulting in a heterogeneous impact. In this context, track recommendations are understood to moderate the relationship between students' SES and key outcomes during the transition from primary to secondary education, such as academic intentions, application behaviour, and admission (or enrollment) to an academic track.

Identifying the moderating role of track recommendations concerning SES and further educational outcomes is challenging in observational studies. To get unbiased estimations and to draw causal inferences, track recommendations should be assigned randomly (Bansak 2021). For obvious ethical reasons, randomisation in this current research was impossible. Thus, biases are incorporated into the estimations, and their transparent reporting is necessary (Clarke et al. 2024).

Potential biases may arise because track recommendations are not independent of students' socioeconomic status but might be influenced by it. Therefore, controlling track recommendation leads to the inclusion of a set of uncontrolled confounders (U) that may influence track recommendation. Examples of these confounders include factors such as ability, self-confidence, effort, parental support, and parental involvement. As illustrated in the right-hand panel of Figure 3, these variables are both influenced by SES and, in turn, influence track recommendations. Since these confounders are not directly controlled, it is impossible to separate the effects of track recommendations from those of the confounders, which introduces bias into the estimation of the moderation effect. Nevertheless, previous research indicates that uncontrolled confounders moderately mediate SES differences (Batruch et al. 2023), implying that potential bias is likely to be small.

Figure 3: Hypothesised relationship of moderation, directed acyclic graphs

Empirical analysis

In the empirical analysis, the following classroom fixed-effect linear probability model is estimated:

$$Y_{ic} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \times TR_{ic} + \beta_3 \times SES_{ic} + \beta_4 \times (TR_{ic} \times SES_{ic}) + \beta_5 \times X_{ic} + \varphi_c + \epsilon_{ic} \quad \text{Eq.1.}$$

In Eq.1. Y_{ic} stands for the outcome of the i -th student in c -th classroom (application intention, application behaviour and admission). TR_{ic} stands for the track recommendation, which is ‘1’ if the teacher recommended the student for the academic track, and ‘0’ otherwise. SES_{ic} stands for students’ SES measured by their mother’s education. It is ‘1’ in the case of high-SES students (mother has a tertiary education) and ‘0’ in the case of middle/low-SES students (mother has less than a tertiary education). The vector X_{ic} contains control variables such as students’ GPA, gender, age, behaviour, and diligence grades, with the latter two introduced as dummy variables. The classroom fixed effects are denoted by φ_c , while ϵ_{ic} is the individual error term. Standard errors are clustered at the school level.

The coefficients of interest are β_3 and the linear combination of β_3 and β_4 . Here β_3 shows the SES gap between those low- and high-SES students who are *not* recommended for the academic track ($TR_{ic} = 0$). In contrast, the linear combination of β_3 and β_4 shows the SES gap between those low- and high-SES students being recommended for the academic track ($TR_{ic} = 1$). The interaction coefficient β_4 reflects the difference between the two SES gaps. None of these coefficients has a causal interpretation.

Results

Figure 4 shows the predicted probabilities (with 95% confidence intervals from Eq.1) for application intention, application behaviour, and admission using the linear probability model. Predictions from the logit models are shown in Appendix Figure A2, revealing substantively similar results across both linear and logistic specifications.

Grey columns on Figure 4 represent students not recommended for the academic track, while black columns represent those recommended for the academic track. The y-axis shows the predicted probabilities in % across four groups of students: low-SES students without an academic track recommendation (N = 358), low-SES students with an academic track recommendation (N = 92), high-SES students without an academic track recommendation (N = 39), and high-SES students with an academic track recommendation (N = 63).

Figure 4: Predicted probabilities from Eq. 1 (linear probability model)

In general, students who are not recommended for the academic track have lower average probabilities of intending to apply, actually applying, and being admitted to the academic track than those who are recommended. Furthermore, high-SES students almost always outperform low-SES students, who consistently lag behind—with the exception of admission outcomes among those who are not recommended for the academic track. In this case, a small and statistically non-significant difference slightly favours low-SES students, likely reflecting imprecise estimates due to the small sample size ($N = 39$), as suggested by the wide confidence intervals.

Figure 5 displays the average marginal SES gaps in percentage points with 95% confidence intervals, estimated using Eq. 1, for application intention, application behaviour, and admission. The corresponding fixed-effects linear probability models are presented in Table 3. Gaps are presented separately for students who are not recommended for the academic track (β_3 , grey circles) and for those who are recommended for the academic track ($\beta_3 + \beta_4$, black circles). Intuitively, the gaps illustrated in Figure 5 reflect the SES differences between the grey and black columns for each outcome in Figure 4, thereby yielding six graphically represented marginal SES gaps.

Note: The SES differences are estimated using classroom fixed-effects OLS regressions, with standard errors clustered at the school level. The SES gaps are statistically significant at the 5% significance level unless they cross the vertical line marked at 0 on the y-axis. Differences between the two SES gaps, marked in grey and black, are tested using the interaction effect (β_4) in Eq. 1, with the corresponding p-value referring to this coefficient. Full regression results are presented in Table A3.

Figure 5: SES differences (in percentage points) for application intentions, application behaviour, and admission rates, with 95% confidence intervals, among students with and without academic track recommendations.

Almost all SES differences are positive, indicating that, among both recommended and non-recommended students, those from low-SES backgrounds have lower average probabilities of intending to apply, actually applying, and being admitted to academic-track secondary schools than their high-SES peers.

Among students who are not recommended for the academic track, SES gaps (β_3) are small—no more than ten percentage points—and not statistically significant at the 5% level. This means that high-SES students had only slightly higher average probabilities of intending to apply, submitting an application to, or gaining admission to an academic secondary track than their low-SES peers.

In contrast, among students recommended for the academic track, the SES gaps ($\beta_3 + \beta_4$) are both statistically significant and substantively large. The average probability of expressing an intention to apply to, submitting an application to, or securing admission to an academic track was approximately 20 percentage points higher among high-SES students than their low-SES peers.

The interaction coefficient, β_4 , reflecting the difference between the two SES-related gaps, is statistically significant for admission to the academic secondary track (a difference of 30 percentage points, $p = 0.005$) but not for the other two outcomes—application intentions and behaviour. Thus, although the adjusted model restricts significant SES differences between non-recommended and recommended students to admission to the secondary track, other SES differences remain substantial, with a gap of around 10 percentage points. Notably, the positive interaction effect between track recommendation and SES (TR \times SES) for admission is particularly striking, as admission ultimately shapes each student’s subsequent educational trajectory.

Table 3: Regression results concerning the coefficients presented in Figure 5, unstandardised coefficients from linear probability models

	(1) Application intention	(2) Application behaviour	(3) Admission
<i>Academic track recommendation (TR), β_2</i>	0.34** (0.09)	0.32** (0.09)	0.29** (0.08)
Tertiary-educated mother (SES), β_3	0.04 (0.09)	0.10 (0.10)	-0.06 (0.07)
TR \times SES, β_4	0.11 (0.12)	0.09 (0.11)	0.30** (0.10)
GPA, in grade 7	0.11** (0.04)	0.10* (0.04)	0.10** (0.04)
Female	0.06* (0.03)	0.03 (0.03)	0.05 (0.03)
Age	-0.01 (0.03)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.03)
Constant	-0.08 (0.53)	-0.16 (0.45)	-0.16 (0.51)
Observations	552	552	552
R-squared	0.56	0.54	0.55
SES gap among students recommended the academic track, Linear combination: $\beta_3 + \beta_4$	0.15+ (0.07)	0.19* (0.08)	0.24** (0.08)

All models include classroom fixed effects and dummies for students’ diligence and behaviour grades. Standard errors are clustered at the school level. Missing values in the covariates are replaced with zeros, and separate dummy variables control for missing status.

Robust standard errors in parentheses

** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, + $p < 0.1$

Discussion

This study has examined how track recommendations moderate the SES differences during the transition from primary to secondary education in Hungary, a school context where teachers' recommendations are non-binding but teachers frequently provide informal advice to their students. It has been argued that even non-binding and informal track recommendations have significant consequences for later educational outcomes. This is the case because academic track recommendation serves as a signal that can empower students, boost their self-confidence, and provide access to crucial information—all of which influence their subsequent educational outcomes (Barone et al., 2018; Keller et al., 2022; Tolsma et al., 2010).

The finding showed that SES differences in application intentions, actual applications, and admission to the academic track were concentrated among students recommended for the academic track. Among these students, SES gaps were large and statistically significant, while they were small and insignificant among students not recommended for the academic track. The difference between these two gaps resulted in a positive interaction effect, which supports the predictions of cultural reproduction theory. In particular, cultural (Bourdieu and Passeron 1977) and institutional (Bowles and Gintis 1976) constraints may prevent low-SES students from fully capitalising on the advantages offered by academic track recommendations.

This study advances the analytical framework by examining SES differences separately for students who are recommended/not recommended for the academic track, thereby revealing distinct mechanisms underlying the SES gap. While low-SES students lagged behind high-SES peers in both groups, the substantive factors driving this disparity differed according to recommendation status.

When students are not recommended for the academic track, the small and statistically insignificant SES gap is consistent with the *disadvantage saturation* mechanism rather than the *compensatory advantage* mechanism. From this perspective, low-SES students are already so severely disadvantaged that an additional setback—such as not receiving a track recommendation—has a relatively smaller marginal effect on them compared to their high-SES peers, who have experienced fewer prior disadvantages. The *disadvantage saturation* mechanism contrasts with the *compensatory advantage* perspective, which suggests that high-SES students compensate more effectively for setbacks. If this were the case, one would expect to find large and statistically significant SES differences among students who are not recommended for the academic track—yet such differences were not found here. Thus, high SES does not appear to compensate for the setback of not receiving an academic track recommendation.

When students are recommended for the academic track, the large and statistically significant SES differences align with the cumulative (dis)advantage mechanism rather than the great equaliser mechanism. This suggests that those already in an advantaged position gain more, while those who are initially disadvantaged gain less from educational advancements, such as receiving an academic track recommendation. This contrasts with the great equaliser thesis, which posits that such advancements allow low-SES students to catch up with their high-SES peers.

Together, these results suggest that SES gaps in later educational outcomes—such as intentions to pursue an academic track, application behaviour, and admission to academic secondary schools—mainly arise among students who are recommended for the academic track. For this reason, high-SES students' advantages in these outcomes may not only stem from track recommendations—a widely recognised factor (Esser 2016; Helbig and Morar 2018)—but also

from institutional processes that block low-SES students from reaching the academic track, even when teachers recommend them for this. Although this study does not directly examine such institutional barriers, potential examples might include admissions tests or admission restrictions (Finger and Solga 2023; Finger et al. 2024) that act as gatekeepers, discouraging low-SES students from pursuing the academic track.

The situation in the Hungarian education system is a revealing example for other tracked systems. Research by Glock et al. (2012) shows that teachers tend to be more biased in their recommendations when the stakes are low and they are not held accountable for the outcomes. The informal and non-binding nature of track recommendations in Hungary may therefore create a low-stakes context that reduces accountability, thereby making underlying patterns in track recommendations more visible. Therefore, the Hungarian example serves as a useful test case for observing potentially more general tendencies in track recommendations.

Several limitations restrict the generalisability of the findings. First, the sample consisted of disadvantaged rural Hungarian primary schools. In these schools, even high-SES students may struggle to access necessary cultural resources, leaving them as similarly constrained as their low-SES peers (Owens 2010). This suggests that the differences between low- and high-SES students might be underestimated here.

Second, the small number of high-SES students—particularly those without an academic track recommendation—results in large confidence intervals and less precise comparisons.

Third, the generally positive interaction effect between SES and track recommendations was significant only for admission outcomes, and not for the other two outcomes—the intention to apply for the academic track and actual applications to this track. This limits the interpretation of the cultural (Bourdieu and Passeron 1977) and institutional (Bowles and Gintis 1976) constraints underlying the positive interaction effect to a single outcome—admission—which represents only the final stage of the transition process. Replication of these findings in larger samples is therefore necessary, as SES differences between those recommended and not recommended for the academic track are non-trivial for the other two outcomes.

Fourth, the results are observational rather than causal; thus, unobserved confounders—such as ability, self-confidence, effort, parental support, and involvement—may bias the estimates.

Lastly, SES was measured by maternal education, which is a widely used indicator (Erola et al. 2016), yet is often criticised for not fully capturing the broader influence of parental background (Thaning and Hällsten 2020).

Despite these limitations, the study clearly suggests that SES differences are generated primarily among students who are recommended for the academic track. Thus, teachers' agency in creating—or even amplifying—SES differences through biased or withheld recommendations may be less influential than previously thought. This novel result is worth considering until more robust causal evidence emerges to address the gap in the literature on how track recommendations moderate SES differences during the transition from primary to secondary education.

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APPENDIX

for the paper entitled

Track Recommendations Moderate Socioeconomic Differences during
the Transition from Primary to Secondary Education

by Tamás Keller

Version: 2025. November 20.

Appendix Tables

Table A1: Characteristics of sample schools relative to all Hungarian primary schools

	(1) Very rich students (%)	(2) Very poor students (%)	(3) Roma students %	(4) Test score, 8th grade	(5) SES	(6) Village (%)	(7) Town (%)	(8) County seed (%)	(9) Budapest (capital city), (%)	(10) Very small school ^{\$} (%)	(11) Small school (%)	(12) Medium- sized school (%)	(13) Large school (%)
Mean: NON sample schools	0.08	0.19	0.21	-0.01	-0.03	0.30	0.13	0.12	0.01	0.32	0.33	0.34	0.08
Mean: sample schools	0.06	0.23	0.31	-0.06	-0.45	0.17	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.47	0.28	0.19	0.06
Mean difference	-0.03+ (0.01)	0.05 (0.04)	0.11+ (0.06)	-0.05 (0.20)	-0.42 (0.20)	0.28** (0.08)	-0.14* (0.06)	-0.08* (0.04)	-0.07+ (0.04)	0.05 (0.04)	0.15+ (0.08)	-0.05 (0.08)	-0.15* (0.07)
Standardised mean difference	-0.20	0.22	0.36	-0.43	-0.55	0.56	-0.29	-0.23	-0.21	0.53	0.33	-0.11	-0.32
No. schools	2,482	2,484	2,474	2,744	2,492	2,576	2,576	2,576	2,576	2,576	2,576	2,576	2,576

Author's calculation based on data from the Hungarian National Assessment of Basic Competencies (NABC) applicable to the cohort of 8th graders in 2022. Same school cohort as those participating in the survey data.

NABC assesses students' mathematics and reading comprehension achievement with a PISA-like test, administered in four 45-minute exams at the end of 8th grade, along with an in-class test supervised by classroom teachers and marked centrally. Furthermore, NABC includes a take-home supplementary questionnaire that contains information on individual students' social backgrounds and home environments. Lastly, NABC deploys a school questionnaire filled out by the school principal, which asks questions about the school context.

The source of data in Columns 1-3 and 6-13 is the NABC school questionnaire, which was answered by the school principal.

The source of data in Column 4 is students' individual test scores aggregated to the school level. Test scores are students' average performance in mathematics and reading comprehension.

Mean differences are calculated using a regression model. The dependent variable corresponds to the variable shown in each column. The independent variable is a dummy coded as '1' if the school was a sample school and '0' otherwise.

Robust standard errors, clustered at the school level, in parentheses.

** p<0.01, * p<0.05, + p<0.1

The source of data in Column 5 is individual students' background data from the NABC background questionnaire aggregated to the school level.

\$ A very small school is a school with a maximum of five teachers (as defined by NABC).

Table A2: Characteristics of students in the sample relative to all eighth-grade Hungarian primary school students in the application process in the academic year 2021/22

	Mean among Non-Sample Students	Mean Difference (Sample Students – Non-Sample Students)	N
Female	0.49	-0.01	83,161
First application to academic secondary school	0.38	-0.07	83,161
% applied academic secondary schools	0.37	-0.07	83,161
GPA, 7th grade, 9 subjects	3.71	-0.06	83,161
Admitted to academic secondary school	0.34	-0.05	80,749
GPA, 5th grade, 5 subjects	3.77	-0.13	79,164
GPA, 6th grade, 5 subjects	3.78	-0.13	79,641
GPA, 7th grade, 5 subjects	3.73	-0.09	83,159
GPA, 8th grade, 5 subjects	3.80	-0.09	83,078

Mean differences are calculated with OLS regressions. Standard errors are clustered at the school level.

** p<0.01, * p<0.05

Source of data: Official statistics on secondary school applications and admissions for the year 2022 (KIFIR data).

Appendix Figures

Figure A1: Raw means of the dependent variable according to SES and track recommendation

Figure A2: Predicted probabilities from Eq. 1 (Logit Model)